

Report on the content and technical structure of the **EUPRO** Infrastructure

AIT: Austrian Institute of Technology

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innovation policy studies"

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Report on the content and technical structure of EUPRO v7.4.11 (Task 6 of WP6)

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1 Basic characteristics

Name and short description of the infrastructure

EUPRO – Database on European Framework Programmes

The EUPRO database comprises information on R&D projects and all participating organizations funded by the European Framework Programmes (FP).

Aim of the database (context of data acquisition)

The EUPRO database is a significant asset of the Innovation Systems Department of AIT used for basic oriented research projects and contract research for national and international customers, such as the European Commission. It facilitates the analysis of participation patterns of organisations in different priorities of the FP and the investigation of collaborative network structures, including their evolution over time and the development of the European Research Area (ERA).

Legal name of operating organization

AIT – Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Database location and type of access (access on site, online, etc.)

EUPRO is accessible onsite at:

AIT – Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Innovation Systems Department
Donau-City-Str. 1
1220 Vienna, Austria

2 Information on substantive content of *EUPRO*

2.1 Definition and description of observations

Units and definition of observations

EUPRO covers information on:

- projects (such as project objectives and achievements, project costs, total funding, start and end date, contract type, information on the call) and
- participations (name of the participating organization, contact person with contact details, organisation type, and geographical location (NUTS2))

Number of observations

EUPRO v7.4.11 comprises information on **63,860 projects** and **337,108 participations**.
Table 1 disaggregates the units of observation by different FPs.

Table 1: EUPRO database - number of projects and participations

Programme	Period	Projects	Participations
FP1	1984 - 1987	3,283	7,929
FP2	1987 - 1991	3,878	19,068
FP3	1990 - 1994	5,528	31,378
FP4	1994 - 1998	14,562	67,858
FP5	1998 - 2002	16,034	78,728
FP6	2002 - 2006	9,709	72,012
FP7*	2007 - 2013	10,866	60,135
Total		63,860	337,108

*Note: Until July 2012

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

Where the data are retrieved from

The core data source for the construction of the EUPRO database is the CORDIS¹ projects database. It contains detailed information on funded projects and project participants of FPs. For the funded projects the CORDIS database lists information on project objectives and achievements, project costs, project funding, temporal location and contract type. It also provides valuable information on the project participants including the full name and address of the organisation, the participating department (partially) and the contact person.

The data on FP collaborations is publicly available. Raw data of the current version (EUPRO v7.4.11) was downloaded in July 2012. We used a wrapper – a type of web scraping program – to extract and structure the information from the website in an automated way. In order to do this, the wrapper opens each project webpage and parses the HTML content. As each webpage follows the same structure it is easy to guide the wrapper to the relevant information, which is then stored in a relational form.

How the data are processed in terms of data cleaning

The quality of the raw data extracted from the CORDIS projects database is not generally sufficient for policy-relevant analyses. AIT has undertaken substantial efforts to improve quality and the level of standardisation of the data and to retrieve and add missing data.

Data cleaning and standardisation includes three major steps:

- identification of unique organisation name,
- identification of unique organisation type, and
- regionalisation (i.e. assignment of geographical locations to European NUTS regions).

The harmonisation of organisations names and the integration of new CORDIS data is ultimately manual, but supported by applying specific matching algorithms developed by AIT. These algorithms are based on statistical properties such as the frequency of adjacent characters in the organisation names and are used to identify similar organisation names that can be attributed to the same organisation. All algorithmically identified name matches are

¹ CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service, <http://cordis.europa.eu/>) is the European Commission's primary public repository and portal to disseminate information on all EU-funded research projects and their results in the broadest sense.

manually checked for accuracy. Regionalisation is based on City-to-Nuts correspondence tables.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

Description of all variables and/or indicators that are given for the main units of observation

Table 2: Description of variables providing information about projects

Variable	Description
RecCtrNr	unique identifier (record control number) for each project in the database, identical with unique identifier of all projects in the CORDIS projects database
Project Reference	(not-unique) project index, for internal use in the European Commission (matches with Project Id in CORDA)
PrgrType (code)	code (1-7) for the names of the specific framework programme types FP1 to FP7
PrgrType	contains the corresponding names of the framework programmes (e.g., Seventh Framework Programme)
Subprogramme Area	full name of the subprogramme areas in each of the framework programmes
PrAcr	subprogramme acronym in the framework programmes (e.g., FP7-Health)
Title	Full title of the project
ProjAcr	(non-unique) project acronym or abbreviation of the project title
Subject Index	one or more of 68 standardized keywords; in the first three framework programmes distinct combinations of subject indices were allocated by the European Commission to projects of the same subprogram; after FP4 the allocation of subject indices to specific subprograms is more ambiguous; caution: allocation of subject indices seems sometimes arbitrary – check reliability of contents of this variable before usage
Other Indexes	additional keywords to characterize project contents, freely chosen by the project team
Objective, GenInfo (general information), Achievements	distinction of these fields not clearly defined, in practice any of these fields may contain objectives or an abstract of the project.
Partners/Project	number of participants in each project; additional generated information, calculated with the help of table “participants_FP1-7”
Contract type	different types of contracts which regulate size, financing and funding of the research projects (e.g., STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project)
Start Date, End Date	day, month and year of project start and end
Duration (in months)	duration of the project in months (data provided by cordis)
Project Cost	official project costs
Project Funding	financing contribution of the European Union; since not all projects are financed completely, figures in “Project Funding” are equal to or smaller than figures in “Project Cost”.
Project Status	current status of the project (accepted, completed, execution) given in the CORDIS projects database in July, 2012
Project URL	official website of the project

Table 3: Description of variables providing information about participating organisations

Variable	Description
RecCtrNr	unique identifier (record control number) for each project in the database, identical with unique identifier of all projects in the CORDIS projects database; corresponds with the entries in the field RecCtrNr in the projects table (Table 2)
Cnr	unique identifier (control number) assigned internally by AIT, as project participants are not uniquely indexed in the CORDIS projects database; all project-relevant information is indicated with “1”, prime contractor with “2”, and remaining participants with “3”, “4”, etc.
stOrg	standardised organisation name; the EUPRO database currently covers a period of more than 30 years during which organisations have changed to mergers, acquisitions and divestitures. At the moment organisations are labeled by their most recent valid name.
stsubentity	standardised identifier for organisational subunits; incomplete raw data on the participating subunits for FP1 to FP6; with the introduction of the Participant Identification Code (PIC) in FP7 such raw data is no longer available
stOrgType	standardised organisation type
Contact Person	name of contact person, without name affixes like titles, etc.
Tel	phone number of contact person
Fax	fax number of contact person
URL	official website of the organisation
sAddress_orig	complete address information
sPostcode	extracted postal code
sCity	extracted city
sRegion	extracted European Regions
stCtry	standardised country codes; country abbreviations are given as ISO 3166-1 Alpha-3 country codes ²
NUTS2	region code according to the NUTS -2 classification scheme (revision 2010)
CtryType	type of FP association of the country in terms of eligibility for funding (FP7)

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

Information on the sectorial classifications used

Table 4: Organisation type

Category	Description
IND	industry
EDU	universities and other educational institutions
ROR	public and private research organisations
GOV	governmental institutions
CON	consultants
NCL	non-commercial/non-profit organisations
OTH	others—mainly special interest groups, like unions, chambers, inter-trade organisations, etc.
N/A	not available

² <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search/code/>

On a (no longer available) CORDIS website³ subject indices were assigned to different themes. Table 5 contains the list of 68 subject indices and the themes to which they were attributed.

³ Thematic Navigation by Subject Index, http://cordis.europa.eu/themes/home_en.html#cloud (accessed: 13/08/2010)

Table 5: Subject Indices and Themes

Subject Index	Theme
VETERINARY AND ANIMAL SCIENCES	Agriculture and food supply
AGRICULTURE	Agriculture and food supply
FOOD	Agriculture and food supply
AGRICULTURAL BIOTECHNOLOGY	Agriculture and food supply
RESOURCES OF THE SEA, FISHERIES	Agriculture and food supply
MEDICINE, HEALTH	Biology and medicine
BIOTECHNOLOGY	Biology and medicine
LIFE SCIENCES	Biology and medicine
HEALTHCARE DELIVERY/SERVICES	Biology and medicine
MEDICAL BIOTECHNOLOGY	Biology and medicine
NUCLEAR FISSION	Energy
NUCLEAR FUSION	Energy
FOSSIL FUELS	Energy
RENEWABLE SOURCES OF ENERGY	Energy
ENERGY STORAGE, ENERGY, TRANSPORT	Energy
ENERGY SAVING	Energy
BIOFUELS	Energy
HYDROGEN AND FUEL CELLS	Energy
OTHER ENERGY TOPICS	Energy
CLEAN COAL TECHNOLOGIES	Energy
METEOROLOGY	Environment and climate
ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION	Environment and climate
RADIATION PROTECTION	Environment and climate
WASTE MANAGEMENT	Environment and climate
RADIOACTIVE WASTE	Environment and climate
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	Environment and climate
EARTH SCIENCES	Environment and climate
CLIMATE CHANGE AND CARBON CYCLE RESEARCH	Environment and climate
WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT	Environment and climate
INDUSTRIAL MANUFACTURE	Industry and industrial technology
MATERIALS TECHNOLOGY	Industry and industrial technology
NANOTECHNOLOGY AND NANOSCIENCES	Industry and industrial technology
INDUSTRIAL BIOTECH	Industry and industrial technology
ELECTRONICS, MICROELECTRONICS	Information and Communication Technology
INFORMATION PROCESSING, INFORMATION SYSTEMS	Information and Communication Technology
TELECOMMUNICATIONS	Information and Communication Technology
AUTOMATION	Information and Communication Technology
ROBOTICS	Information and Communication Technology
ICT APPLICATIONS	Information and Communication Technology
NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES	Information and Communication Technology
MEASUREMENT METHODS	Research in practice
MATHEMATICS; STATISTICS	Research in practice
REFERENCE MATERIALS	Research in practice
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH	Research in practice
PROJECT MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGIES	Research in practice
COORDINATION, COOPERATION	Research in practice
POLICIES	Research in practice

LEGISLATION, REGULATIONS	Research in practice
FORECASTING	Research in practice
RESEARCH ETHICS	Research in practice
EVALUATION	Research outputs
STANDARDS	Research outputs
INNOVATION, TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER	Research outputs
BUSINESS ASPECTS	Research outputs
INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS	Research outputs
SOCIAL ASPECTS	Social and Economic Concerns
EDUCATION, TRAINING	Social and Economic Concerns
INFORMATION, MEDIA	Social and Economic Concerns
ECONOMIC ASPECTS	Social and Economic Concerns
REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT	Social and Economic Concerns
EMPLOYMENT ISSUES	Social and Economic Concerns
SAFETY	Social and Economic Concerns
SECURITY	Social and Economic Concerns
CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY	Transport and Construction
TRANSPORT	Transport and Construction
AEROSPACE TECHNOLOGY	Transport and Construction
SPACE AND SATELLITE RESEARCH	Transport and Construction
OTHER TECHNOLOGY	Transport and Construction

Information on the temporal coverage used

EUPRO v7.4.11 covers all EU FP projects and participants starting from 1984, with the latest update in July 2012.

Information on the geographical coverage and classifications used

Since we have information on the geographical location of the project participants in the EUPRO database, we can analyse their geographical distribution across Europe at the country-level as well as on the regional level by assigning organisation to European NUTS regions⁴ using NUTS classification revision 2010⁵.

EUPRO covers participations from the following countries:

- *EU 28 Member States*
- *Associated countries* (with science and technology cooperation agreements that involved contributing to the framework programme budget)⁶:
Switzerland; Israel; Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein; Turkey, Croatia, the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia and Serbia; Albania and Montenegro; Bosnia & Herzegovina; Faroe Islands; Republic of Moldova
- *Third Countries* (countries that are not Member States, nor associated countries)⁷

⁴ including the analogous territorial descriptions for Switzerland and Norway

⁵ History of NUTS, http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/nuts_nomenclature/history_nuts (accessed: 24/04/2014)

⁶ FP7 Third Country Agreements, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/fp7/116018/fp7-third-country-agreements_en.pdf (accessed: 24/04/2014)

- *International Cooperation Partner Countries (ICPC)*⁸: Countries eligible for EU funding from Africa, Asia, Caribbean, Pacific, Eastern Europa and Central Asia (EECA), Latin America, Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC) and Western Balkan Countries (WBC) (for the total list see Annex, Table A 1)
- *High-income countries* (normally not eligible for EU funding): United States of America, Canada, Japan, the Republic of Korea, Singapore, Australia and New Zealand, Taiwan, Hong Kong and Macao, Vatican, San Marino, Monaco and Andorra.

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

Information on the number of missing values

EUPRO v7.4.11 comprises data on 63,860 projects and 337,108 participations (see Table 1). The following two tables give an overview of the number and ratio of missing values for each variable.

Table 6: Number and ratio of missing values of project data

Variable	Missing values	
	Count	Ratio
RecCtrNr	none	0%
Project Reference	none	0%
PrgrType (code)	none	0%
PrgrType	none	0%
Subprogramme Area	15,296	24%
PrAcr	none	0%
Title	1	0%
ProjAcr	24,271	38%
Subject Index	3	0%
Other Indexes	54,540	85%
Objective	20,592	32%
GenInfo	43,383	68%
Achievements	55,940	88%
Partners/Project	none	0%
Contract type	13,759	22%
Start Date	2,144	3%
End Date	2,955	5%
Duration (in months)	8,863	14%
Project Cost	27,422	43%
Project Funding	22,919	36%
Project Status	none	0%
Project URL	58,497	92%

⁷ Cooperation with Third Country Participants in an EC funded FP7 multi-partner research project, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/fp7/90400/guideline-third-country-participants_en.pdf

⁸ List of International Cooperation Partner Countries (ICPC) - Annex 1 of Work Programme 2013 Cooperation, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/fp7/206006/wp-2013-annex-1-icpc-list_en.pdf, (accessed: 24/04/2014)

Table 7: Number and ratio of missing values of participant's data

Variable	Missing values	
	Count	Ratio
RecCtrNr	0	0%
Cnr	0	0%
stOrg	3,680	1%
stsubentity	287,245	85%
stOrgType	4,515	1%
Contact Person	68,423	20%
Tel	133,451	40%
Fax	142,477	42%
URL	244,810	73%
sAddress_orig	1,227	0%
sPostcode	129,267	38%
sCity	14,216	4%
sRegion	54,495	16%
	(34,655 in EU 28)	11%
stCtry	1,062	0%
NUTS2	13,679	4%
CtryType	0	0%

Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system

In general, the original database CORDIS constitutes a reliable resource on all FP projects and participations. However, in some few cases information is incomplete or inconsistent, as for instance the starting and ending dates of projects, in particular for earlier FPs.

In regard to the data acquisition and retrieving system the data is sound and complete. The retrieving system used was a wrapper – a type of web scraping program.

- *Soundness*: The raw data which is extracted from the CORDIS website is copied one-on-one and simply restructured in a relational form.
- *Completeness*: The wrapper parses the HTML content of all project webpages and is guided to the relevant information. Each webpage follows a given structure. Hence, each piece of information is located in the same place and information won't be missed by the wrapper.

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

Legal issues concerning access of the database

A complete opening of the database is not foreseen, not least in order to avoid an uncontrolled proliferation of data sets and thus to ensure quality control. Precise rules for access to EUPRO will be defined as an essential precondition for the opening for EUPRO.

Owner of EUPRO raw data

AIT Austrian Institute of Technology

Copyright holder for underlying EU FP raw data: © European Union, 1994-2014

Source: CORDIS, <http://cordis.europa.eu/>

Current practice for opening up of the database to external users

While the database is primarily a major asset of the Innovation Systems Department of AIT, and used for both scientific research projects and contract research for national and international customers, AIT has already provided access to data in selected cases in the past, mainly for scientific purposes (joint projects and publications).

Legal necessities for potential opening procedures

In general, access will be possible for joint projects and scientific publications. In addition, the provision of specific extracts of EUPRO, by way of on-site access at AIT premises, is planned. Due to the size and complexity of EUPRO, a dedicated local training and close collaboration with AIT staff is foreseen, usually requiring local presence for some 2-3 weeks.

4 Technical structure of *EUPRO*

4.1 Information on the data base system

Current data base system used

EUPRO is realized as Microsoft Access 2007 database.

Planned future technical changes concerning data base system

None

4.2 Technical variable definition

Labelling and data type of all variables

Table 8: Data type of variables providing information about projects

Variable	Data type
RecCtrNr	Number
Project Reference	Text
PrgrType (code)	Number
PrgrType	Text
Subprogramme Area	Memo
PrAcr	Text
Title	Text
ProjAcr	Text
Subject Index	Memo
Other Indexes	Memo
Objective	Memo
GenInfo	Memo
Achievements	Memo
Partners/Project	Number
Contract type	Text
Start Date	Date
End Date	Date
Duration (in months)	Number
Project Cost	Number
Project Funding	Number
Project Status	Text
Project URL	Text

Table 9: Data type of variables providing information about participating organisations

Variable	Data type
RecCtrNr	Text
Cnr	Number
stOrg	Text
stsubentity	Text
stOrgType	Text
Contact Person	Text
Tel	Text
Fax	Text
URL	Text
sAddress_orig	Memo
sPostcode	Text
sCity	Text
sRegion	Text
stCtry	Text
NUTS2	Text
CtryType	Text

4.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model of EUPRO

Definition of single tables

EUPRO currently consists of six tables (Figure 1): *projects_FP1-7* and *participants_FP1-7*

Figure 1: EUPRO Entity Relationship Model

Relation between the tables via unique identifiers

projects_FP1-7 and *participants_FP1-7* are linked via RecCtrNr (record control number), which is a unique identifier for each project in the database and identical to the unique identifier for the project in the CORDIS projects database. The four remaining tables explain abbreviations used in the respective variables.

4.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures

Technical information on interfaces with other infrastructures (e.g. web interface for data search. etc.)

At the current stage, no interfaces are planned. Potential web interfaces may be discussed and implemented during the course of the project, for instance for the provision of specific extracts of aggregated data (e.g., number of organisations/participations per country).

5 Further planning of the opening of *EUPRO*

Document concrete steps towards opening of the respective dataset

By establishing a link to various other data sources (e.g. patent data, publications, structural data on firms, universities and PROs) the scientific potential of EUPRO shall be further enhanced. The opening date within RISIS will take place in accordance with other RISIS facilities. Accreditation and access will be formalised in accordance to Task 4 of RISIS WP6.

- New identifier at organisational level (in accordance with WP8)
- Integration of new variables (e.g. NABS code, etc.)
- Adaption to classification schemes defined in other workpackages (e.g., NUTS, organisation type, etc.)

Necessary updates and/or technical changes

The EUPRO database is regularly updated by AIT, usually every second year.

In view of the growing differentiation of frameworks for R&D collaboration in Europe, not the least due to the reinforcement of multilateral arrangements among Member States, further efforts in terms of data retrieval, standardization and refinement will need to be made in the coming years in order to ensure the comprehensive coverage of EUPRO. We will thus extend the EUPRO data set by integrating additional multilateral funding data such as Joint Programming Initiatives, European Technology Platforms, Art. 185-Initiatives, EUREKA, ERANET and COST.

Potentially, a new database model will be defined in an updated version EUPRO. In this version, it is foreseen to add a new organisational table, listing organisations that are linked to projects. The new database model will be developed in accordance to other WPs, in particular the activities in WP8 on the organizational registry.

Changing legal conditions for accessing the dataset or parts of the dataset

The legal access conditions will basically stay the same. Depending on the accreditation systems developed under Task 4 in WP6, changed access conditions will be defined during the course of the project.

Suggestions for example results to be presented at the RISIS week 2015 on the use of the dataset in order to demonstrate its value added (e.g. in conjunction with another dataset)

It can be suggested to use a joint analysis between AIT and USI, joining data from EUMIDA/ETER with EUPRO to explain university participation in FPs by different exogenous factors. Since it is the first matching of two RISIS facilities directly contributing to address a policy relevant research questions, it may suit well to be presented at the RISIS week 2015.

6 Annex

Table A 1: List of International Cooperation Partner Countries (ICPC) participating in EU FP

Country	Code	Type of Country
ANGOLA	AGO	ICPC - Africa
BENIN	BEN	ICPC - Africa
BOTSWANA	BWA	ICPC - Africa
BURKINA FASO	BFA	ICPC - Africa
BURUNDI	BDI	ICPC - Africa
CAMEROON	CMR	ICPC - Africa
CAPE VERDE	CPV	ICPC - Africa
CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC	CAF	ICPC - Africa
CHAD	TCD	ICPC - Africa
CONGO	COG	ICPC - Africa
CONGO, DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC	COD	ICPC - Africa
EQUATORIAL GUINEA	GNQ	ICPC - Africa
ERITREA	ERI	ICPC - Africa
ETHIOPIA	ETH	ICPC - Africa
GABON	GAB	ICPC - Africa
GAMBIA	GMB	ICPC - Africa
GHANA	GHA	ICPC - Africa
GUINEA	GIN	ICPC - Africa
GUINEA-BISSAU	GNB	ICPC - Africa
KENYA	KEN	ICPC - Africa
LESOTHO	LSO	ICPC - Africa
LIBERIA	LBR	ICPC - Africa
MADAGASCAR	MDG	ICPC - Africa
MALAWI	MWI	ICPC - Africa
MALI	MLI	ICPC - Africa
MAURITANIA	MRT	ICPC - Africa
MAURITIUS	MUS	ICPC - Africa
MOZAMBIQUE	MOZ	ICPC - Africa
NAMIBIA	NAM	ICPC - Africa
NIGER	NER	ICPC - Africa
NIGERIA	NGA	ICPC - Africa
RWANDA	RWA	ICPC - Africa
SAO TOME AND PRINCIPE	STP	ICPC - Africa
SENEGAL	SEN	ICPC - Africa
SEYCHELLES	SYC	ICPC - Africa
SIERRA LEONE	SLE	ICPC - Africa
SOMALIA	SOM	ICPC - Africa
SOUTH AFRICA	ZAF	ICPC - Africa
SUDAN	SDN	ICPC - Africa
SWAZILAND	SWZ	ICPC - Africa
TANZANIA	TZA	ICPC - Africa
TOGO	TGO	ICPC - Africa
UGANDA	UGA	ICPC - Africa
ZAMBIA	ZMB	ICPC - Africa
ZIMBABWE	ZWE	ICPC - Africa
AFGHANISTAN	AFG	ICPC - Asia
BANGLADESH	BGD	ICPC - Asia
BHUTAN	BTN	ICPC - Asia
CAMBODIA	KHM	ICPC - Asia

CHINA	CHN	ICPC - Asia
INDIA	IND	ICPC - Asia
INDONESIA	IDN	ICPC - Asia
IRAN	IRN	ICPC - Asia
IRAQ	IRQ	ICPC - Asia
LAO PEOPLE'S DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC	LAO	ICPC - Asia
MALAYSIA	MYS	ICPC - Asia
MALDIVES	MDV	ICPC - Asia
MONGOLIA	MNG	ICPC - Asia
MYANMAR	MMR	ICPC - Asia
NEPAL	NPL	ICPC - Asia
OMAN	OMN	ICPC - Asia
PAKISTAN	PAK	ICPC - Asia
PHILIPPINES	PHL	ICPC - Asia
SRI LANKA	LKA	ICPC - Asia
THAILAND	THA	ICPC - Asia
VIET NAM	VNM	ICPC - Asia
YEMEN	YEM	ICPC - Asia
BARBADOS	BRB	ICPC - Carribean
CUBA	CUB	ICPC - Carribean
DOMINICAN REPUBLIC	DOM	ICPC - Carribean
GUYANA	GUY	ICPC - Carribean
HAITI	HTI	ICPC - Carribean
JAMAICA	JAM	ICPC - Carribean
SAINT LUCIA	LCA	ICPC - Carribean
SURINAME	SUR	ICPC - Carribean
TRINIDAD AND TOBAGO	TTO	ICPC - Carribean
ARMENIA	ARM	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
AZERBAIJAN	AZE	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
BELARUS	BLR	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
GEORGIA	GEO	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
KAZAKHSTAN	KAZ	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
KYRGYZSTAN	KGZ	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
Russian Federation	RUS	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
TAJIKISTAN	TJK	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
TURKMENISTAN	TKM	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
UKRAINE	UKR	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
UZBEKISTAN	UZB	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
ARGENTINA	ARG	ICPC - Latin America
BOLIVIA, PLURINATIONAL STATE OF	BOL	ICPC - Latin America
BRAZIL	BRA	ICPC - Latin America
CHILE	CHL	ICPC - Latin America
COLOMBIA	COL	ICPC - Latin America
COSTA RICA	CRI	ICPC - Latin America
ECUADOR	ECU	ICPC - Latin America
EL SALVADOR	SLV	ICPC - Latin America
GUATEMALA	GTM	ICPC - Latin America
HONDURAS	HND	ICPC - Latin America
MEXICO	MEX	ICPC - Latin America
NICARAGUA	NIC	ICPC - Latin America
PANAMA	PAN	ICPC - Latin America
PARAGUAY	PRY	ICPC - Latin America
PERU	PER	ICPC - Latin America
URUGUAY	URY	ICPC - Latin America

VENEZUELA, BOLIVARIAN REPUBLIC OF	VEN	ICPC - Latin America
ALGERIA	DZA	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
EGYPT	EGY	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
Jordan	JOR	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
LEBANON	LBN	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
Libya	LBY	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
MOROCCO	MAR	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
SYRIA	SYR	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
TUNISIA	TUN	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
FIJI	FJI	ICPC - Pacific
PAPUA NEW GUINEA	PNG	ICPC - Pacific
SAMOA	WSM	ICPC - Pacific
SOLOMON ISLANDS	SLB	ICPC - Pacific
TONGA	TON	ICPC - Pacific
VANUATU	VUT	ICPC - Pacific